

Encampments and the Unshackling of Study

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In a year of genocidal horrors in Palestine and confusion in the United States about how to resist, the student encampments of Spring 2024 – beautiful, messy, flawed, and experimental – have become a testament to the possibility of confronting intransigent power by refusing its terms: refusing to leave, refusing to be diverted from core demands to divest from war, and refusing weaponized debates over safety and antisemitism. While it is still too early to fully assess the impact of these encampments, they have already changed the political terrain in noticeable ways.

Restrictions on the study of Zionism have been built over decades through a variety of means, among them attacks on Arab and anti-Zionist faculty (Campbell 1985; Asare 2024), cancellation of classes (Campion 2017), and campaigns to subject antiracist curricula to hostile “stakeholder” approval (Gelman 2023). The effort by conservative, Israel-focused donors to build Zionist knowledge into university infrastructure by investing in conservative forms of Jewish and Israel studies is detailed in Hil Aked’s worthy book *Friends of Israel* (Verso, 2023). In the past year, the timeline of this infrastructure-building has accelerated. At least a dozen campuses with strong anti-Zionist teaching and student organizing have seen the proliferation of task forces and centers on

antisemitism, much of whose work so far has been to reinforce the repressive International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance’s (IHRA) definition of antisemitism (AAUP 2022) and mischaracterizations of anti-genocide protest (Bernstein 2024).

The encampments have been a counterforce, bringing thousands of students into the study of Zionism in the context of colonialism and resistance. This study has included research on universities’ investments in weapons and surveillance industries, as well as their financial structures, which students undertook in the course of demanding divestment. Students found that universities – already understood as major capital actors in the sphere of real estate – drive hundreds of billions of dollars in endowment investments. A report from the Anti-Defamation League’s financial arm JLens, aiming to counter divestment campaigns, announced that 10-year profits from such investments at just five universities amount to \$33.2 billion (JLens 2024). Student researchers at MIT found that direct research projects with the Israeli military were producing dystopian horrors, including robotic swarms tracking moving targets, quantum computing for particle-level surveillance and enhanced weapons precision, and military AI systems like that currently targeting Gazans en masse (“Scientists Against Genocide En-

campment at MIT” 2024; Iraqi 2024).

The encampments’ interventions in study also stemmed from their wide-ranging community education programming. They gathered under the umbrella of National Students for Justice in Palestine’s call for a borderless “Popular University for Gaza,” where scholars and organizers engaged in collective study of anticolonial resistance, regional history and movements, social and political theory, psychology, capital, militarism, the university itself, and their interconnections with Zionism and Palestine (National Students for Justice in Palestine 2024). Questions that are now dangerous to undertake in the formal space of the university – interrogations of the notion of “terror” and violence, among others – were discussable, and discussed.

This liberated education reached far past campus gatherings, traveling through social media and the new genre of “encampment essay,”—writing by students and other participants from and about these spaces. Even though one-off classes do not permit much detail or depth, and social media sharing even less, encampment programming marked out overlapping areas of study. These areas included anticolonial texts, and transnational context that defied long-standing pressures to study Zionism only as a force confined to the borders of Israel, specific to Jewishness, and from the standpoint of its advocates. I saw this broadening of scope among my own public policy students, on a campus where students were closely watching encampments elsewhere. Encampment framings animated my students’ study, leading them to explore how state interests in repression and expansionism permeate U.S. political culture, and how Zionist institutions are interconnected with these commitments.

As targets attacked by officials, NGOs, and media, the encampments provided a public laboratory in which Zionism presented itself for study. We may never know the full extent of the interventions of conservative donors and institutions like the Anti-Defamation League (ADL) and the Academic Engagement Network (AEN) in lining up university administrations behind violent repression of political speech on campus, denunciation of their own faculty, and spurious claim that the encampments made Jewish or Zionist students “unsafe.” But even in mainstream media, the news cycle regularly tossed up examples that made it clear such repression was cultivated by major political forces, rather than a natural administrative response to protest and teaching. For example, a leaked WhatsApp chat revealed that a dozen Zionist billionaires quietly pressured NYC Mayor Eric Adams to deploy militarized police against students—shortly before Adams did just that (Natanson and Felton 2024). Two groups of Congressmembers gave press conferences charging that Columbia was dangerously antisemitic – in front of an encampment preparing to hold Passover services (Solender 2024; Solomon 2024). Such transparent moves to activate repression and generate disinformation may only have been instructive to those paying attention, but the encampments were sites of rapt political attention extending well beyond the organized left.

One result of this massive collective pushback against hegemonic Zionist narratives and knowledge production – a major achievement of the encampments – is the mainstreaming of discussion about Zionism as a power structure and anti-Zionism as its opposition. This is evident in the body of writing that circulated from and about the encampments, particularly in student news-

papers and social media, but also reaching as far as the New York Times (Rosman 2024).

It was evident in the anti-Zionist rap anthem “Hind’s Hall,” released by Macklemore in May 2024. For me, this shift has been tangible in conversation with family and neighbors: openly naming Zionism as the animating force behind the genocide, and as an unfolding narrative in right-wing U.S. politics, is newly permissible. Of course, this victory does not belong only to the encampments. It has also been the logical conclusion of Israeli leaders’ fighters’ and civilians’ relentless public affirmations that they are pursuing genocide in order to realize Zionism, and by Palestinians’ documentation of their efforts to survive it. But it was the encampments that made the operations of Zionist politics visible in the U.S. and educated a wide range of observers on how to interpret them.

The knowledge generated by the encampments is now under severe attack. For example, NYU, Columbia, and Barnard have banned the use of the word “Zionist” in ways that identify it as an objectionable political ideology and invite weaponized claims that it is a coded substitute for anti-Jewish bias. The University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign has made “Zionist” a protected identity, taking up a call from lawfare organizations like the Brandeis Center and advocates like the ADL, Hillel, and the American Jewish Committee. These same groups have lodged a mountain of Title VI complaints and lawsuits alleging that criticism of Zionism amounts to discrimination against Jewish students on many campuses. Additionally, Congress is considering multiple bills that would codify the IHRA definition in federal law and penalize violators.

Meanwhile, movement groups are claiming

and defending the space made by the encampments to think and talk, both structurally and analytically, about Zionism. Scholars can defend this space in the same way, by simply and forthrightly articulating the terms of our study. Student organizing has created a precious opening for critical thought, a shift from comprehending repression to resisting it, as well as a space enabling academic study that escapes the constraints of a captured university. Following their lead, we can and must refuse the terms imposed by the powers enacting genocide. ♦

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